

Studies on Zeta Potential of Particles of (i) Sodium Oleate, (ii) Oleic Acid and their Mixtures Dispersed in Water

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In this paper, Zeta potential of two component systems $H_2O + Na$ oleate, $H_2O + Oleic$ acid as well as of a three component system, $H_2O + Na$ oleate + Oleic acid has been studied with an ultramicroscope fitted with a special type of electrophoretic cell. It has been found that in both the two component systems, the Zeta potential decreases gradually and then increases with the increase of sodium oleate solution or oleic acid solution but when the three components are mixed together, two peaks are found. An attempt has been made to explain the results.

McBain¹ in his earlier work postulated that solubilized solutions are thermodynamically stable. He studied a number of thermodynamic properties *e.g.*, vapour pressure, freezing point, osmotic pressure etc., and concluded that in such solutions, different kinds of micells are formed; these micells are weakly charged but no proof was given by him on thermodynamic stability. It is suggested by Chatterji recently that McBain's ideas require further investigation. Later on, Winsor³ in 1968 points out that McBain's statement on thermodynamic stability of solubilized solutions needs active consideration. In this paper, mobility and then Zeta potential of Sodium Oleate solution and Oleic acid emulsion, separately and then of the mixture of two, (mixing ratio 1 : 1), have been studied by a special type electrophoretic cell fitted in the ultramicroscope. (magnification of the eye piece and objective being X_{10} , X_{15} respectively).

Materials used : Sodium oleate (B.D.H.), Oleic Acid (B.D.H.), double distilled water (conductivity 2.72×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹). Oleic acid was purified by crystallisation on freezing and then by distilling.

Apparatus used : Ultramicroscope, dry battery, microphoretic cell.

(a) *Microphoretic cell* : A cell of Mattson^{5,6,7} type was used. The cell was constructed by taking a pyrex rod having a capillary of 3 mm. diameter. The faces were ground at right angles and the solid angle was kept at about 90°. Two cups (10 cm. each) were fixed at the two ends of the cell to fill the solutions and to dip the platinum electrodes. One lower end of the cell was joined by a stopcock to drain out water to clear the inner surface of the cell. The cell was fixed firmly on the optical bench of the ultramicroscope. The graticules

1. McBain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 2610; 1938, **60**, 223; 1940, **62**, 2855; 1944, **66**, 9.
2. A. C. Chatterji, Private Communication, 1965.
3. P. A. Winsor, *Chemical Review*, **1**, 1968.
4. N. R. Dhar, Private Communication, 1969.
5. M. C. Rastogi, Ph.D. Thesis, Cambridge University, 1958.
6. B. Swaroop, Ph.D. Thesis, 1965.
7. J. Mattson, *J Physical Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 1532; 1933, **37**, 223.

of the eye piece were calibrated against a standard ruled stage micrometer. The grating spacing came out to be 46.6μ where $\mu = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ cm.

(b) *Centering of the cell* : A fine scratch was made on the surface of the cell for locating its surface. The centering of the cell was carried out with the help of this scratch using the X_{10} eye piece.

The objective of the ultramicroscope was fixed in that position of the cell where the maximum number of velocity readings could be obtained. The distance through which the objective was moved for the above purpose was 7.1 mm. This was obtained by first fixing the objective at the fine scratch on the surface and then lowering it with the help of the screws. Thus, a velocity curve was obtained by using a negatively charged silver iodide sol having a strength of 1.5 millimoles per litre. The mobility of this sol was determined at the stationery level. It was found to be $3.1 \mu/\text{sec}$ per volt/cm. The value agrees well with that obtained by Rastogi^{5,6}, Van Gills⁸ and Kruyt⁹.

Electrode used : Platinum foils riveted in platinum wire, fused in pyrex glass were used as electrodes. They were platinized by dry battery having a commutator for reversing the direction of the current. The coating was dark and adsorbed chlorine was removed by an electrical device. The electrodes were kept in distilled water after use.

Preparation of solutions : Sodium Oleate was dried and for preparing the solution of different concentrations from $10^{-6}M$ to $10^{-2}M$, it was weighed in 25 ml. dry graduated flask and the solution was made up by pH 4.5 water by gently shaking the flask to avoid bubbling. From this solution, solutions of different concentrations were prepared by dilution method and pH 4.5 water was used (to avoid hydrolysis). Similarly Oleic acid emulsion was prepared by weighing and then diluting it with water.

Measurement of mobility : The cell was filled with hot chromic acid for 24 hr. and then with $M/1000$ Sodium fluoride solution and finally washed thoroughly with running water. Next it was rinsed with the solution several times to saturate the inner surface of the cell specially in the lower concentration range, and the solution was finally filled. The velocity of the globules was observed across four graticule divisions. After each measurement, the direction of the current was reversed and at least six readings were taken. The current was switched off and turned on again when taking the next measurements. Twelve velocity measurements were taken for each concentration and the mean was taken. After each measurement, the cell was thoroughly cleaned and filled with benzene and acetone to remove greasy spot. The calibration was checked again by silver iodide sol^{5,6}. The experiment was performed at room temperature (35°), since no arrangement for water circulating system was possible to maintain the temperature.

DISCUSSION

The mobility of the micells in sodium oleate solution and emulsion of oleic acid and then the mobility of micells in the mixture of the two, have been observed and the Zeta

8. Von Gills and Kryut, *Kolloid Beih.*, 1937, **45**, 60.

9. Hückel *Physik Z.*, 1924, **25**, 204.

potential was calculated using Huckel equations^{9,10,11} *i.e.*, where the micells have been assumed as spherical, ϵ the dielectric constant and η , the viscosity. The variation for Zeta potential was corrected using Henry equation¹¹.

It is seen that the value of Zeta potential is high before relaxation correction. Hence, correction due to relaxation effect has been applied to the value of Zeta potential in equation (1). From the electrophoretic equation derived by Overbeek for symmetrical electrolytes, the relaxation effect has been accounted and true Zeta potential (Table I) has been calculated before and after due correction from the following equation¹².

$$\mu = \frac{e\xi}{6\pi\eta} \left[f_1 K(a) - Z^2 \left(\frac{ef}{kt} \right) f_3(Ka) - \frac{\rho_+ + \rho_-}{2ek} \cdot \frac{\epsilon k t}{e\pi\eta e} \left(\frac{e\xi}{kt} \right)^2 f_4(Ka) \right] \quad (2)$$

where μ is the mobility, ϵ the dielectric constant, η its viscosity, T absolute temp., k the reciprocal of Debye Hückel¹³ thickness, e the electronic charge, K the Boltzman's constant, ρ_+ , ρ_- the frictional coefficient for cation and anions, Ka is identical with Henry¹⁴ function and $f_3(Ka)$, $f_4(Ka)$ are the functions, the value of which is given by tabulated data of Overbeek¹².

It is seen from the table that true Zeta potential gradually decreases on increasing the concentration of emulsion of Oleic acid upto the concentration $4.65 \times 10^{-6} M$ and then the fall is rapid from 26.36 millivolt to 12 millivolt in the range of $4.65 \times 10^{-7} M$ to $1.58 \times 10^{-6} M$ and then nearly becomes constant at 10.21 millivolt. Similarly sodium oleate solution of different concentrations from $10^{-7} M$ to $10^{-2} M$ was filled in, one by one in the cell and the mobility of the ions was observed. It is seen that mobility is nearly constant at very low concentration range ($10^{-7} M$ to $10^{-6} M$) and it falls sharply and then the curve follows a parabolic path and then the mobility and hence Zeta potential increases after the concentration of $7.2 \times 10^{-4} M$. Next 10 ml. of sodium oleate solution and 10 ml. oleic acid emulsion of equal concentration were mixed and put in the electrophoretic cell as usual for 4 hr for complete solubilization and the mobility was measured. It is seen from the table that mobility or Zeta potential decreases sharply in the range of $1 \times 10^{-7} M$ to $8.9 \times 10^{-7} M$, increases in the parabolic path ($y^2 = 4mx$) (maximum value of Zeta potential 18.07 mv), falls again to a minimum value (10.46 mv) at a concentration of $4.7 \times 10^{-5} M$ and then increases again on a parabolic path giving a maxima (22.64 mv) and after another fall, rises again continuously. Here it is seen that as reported earlier, two peaks at concentrations of $7.9 \times 10^{-6} M$ and $1.34 \times 10^{-4} M$ have been obtained giving Zeta potential 18.07 mv and 22.44 mv respectively.

The two peaks indicate that different kinds of soluble charge transfer complexes are formed and after 10^{-4} molar concentration, solubilization stops. In between the region $6.34 \times 10^{-7} M$ to $6.34 \times 10^{-6} M$, the field becomes bright when the particles are viewed through

10. Loeb McBain, Colloid Science, D.C. Health and Company, Boston, U.S.A., page 131, 1950 edition.
11. J. Henry, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 997.
12. Overbeek, *Kolloid, Beih.*, 1943, **54**, 287.
13. Debye Hückle, *Z. Physik*, 1923, **24**, 185.
14. Henry, *Trans. Faraday Society*, 1948, **44**, 1021.
15. Houwink, *Kolloid Z.*, 1957, **151**, 143.

the ultramicroscope and on further increase of concentration of sodium oleate and oleic acid (mixing ratio 1 : 1) upto $1.518 \times 10^{-3}M$, the brightness of the particle increased while in both the cases of sodium oleate solution and oleic acid emulsion, perhaps the oily drops are formed at higher concentration which are quite visible in the ultramicroscope in between the range of concentrations $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ to $1 \times 10^{-3}M$.

TABLE

Electrokinetic properties (Zeta potential) before and after relaxation correction at 35° (pH = 4.5)

Two component system (1) H₂O+Sodium oleate. (2) H₂O+Oleic Acid
Three component system (1) H₂O+Sodium oleate+Oleic Acid Mixing ratio 1 : 1

S. No.	Conc.	log conc.	Apparent	True	Apparent	True	Apparent	True	Remarks
			Zeta potential of two com-ponent system (Na oleate) +H ₂ O	Zeta potential of two com-ponent system (Na oleate) +H ₂ O	Zeta potential of two com-ponent system (H ₂ O+Oleic acid)	Zeta potential of two com-ponent system (H ₂ O+Oleic acid)	Zeta potential of three com-ponent system (H ₂ O+Oleic acid +Na oleate)	Zeta potential of three com-ponent system (H ₂ O+Oleic acid +Na oleate)	
1.	$7.9 \times 10^{-8}M$	8.8976	33.52 mv	32.62 mv	30.01 mv	30.03 mv	21.63 mv	20.53 mv	Solubilized
2.	$1.57 \times 10^{-7}M$	7.1959	33.26 "	32.34 "	28.56 "	28.62 "	17.34 "	16.43 "	"
3.	3.17 "	7.5011	33.22 "	32.22 "	27.07 "	27.12 "	6.446 "	6.441 "	"
4.	4.696 "	7.6604	33.10 "	32.02 "	26.42 "	26.36 "	1.352 "	1.352 "	"
5.	7.9 "	7.8976	31.62 "	31.64 "	12.11 "	12.12 "	1.274 "	1.264 "	"
6.	$1.58 \times 10^{-6}M$	6.1987	30.01 "	30.01 "	11.56 "	11.54 "	1.376 "	1.362 "	"
7.	3.17 "	6.5011	24.02 "	24.12 "	11.56 "	10.76 "	11.15 "	11.05 "	"
8.	4.755 "	6.6772	21.82 "	21.74 "	11.54 "	10.66 "	12.55 "	12.04 "	"
9.	7.9 "	6.8976	16.53 "	16.41 "	11.56 "	10.92 "	18.77 "	18.07 "	"
10.	$1.58 \times 10^{-5}M$	5.1987	14.02 "	13.17 "	11.54 "	10.87 "	17.75 "	17.65 "	"
11.	3.07 "	5.4871	10.02 "	9.16 "	11.57 "	10.72 "	15.52 "	15.42 "	"
12.	4.755 "	5.6772	9.62 "	8.62 "	11.50 "	10.62 "	10.42 "	10.46 "	"
13.	$1.32 \times 10^{-4}M$	4.1206	8.62 "	8.13 "	11.50 "	10.63 "	22.40 "	24.44 "	"
14.	1.825 "	4.2613	8.12 "	7.93 "	11.50 "	10.52 "	21.07 "	21.07 "	"
15.	2.85 "	4.6609	8.45 "	7.83 "	11.50 "	10.31 "	16.73 "	16.03 "	"
16.	7.3 "	4.8633	8.22 "	7.73 "	11.50 "	10.14 "	22.61 "	26.61 "	Not
17.	$1.12 \times 10^{-3}M$	3.0492	8.12 "	7.83 "	11.50 "	10.10 "	32.20 "	32.14 "	Solubilized
18.	1.465 "	3.1644	8.01 "	7.93 "	11.50 "	10.06 "	32.20 "	32.14 "	"
19.	7.9 "	2.8976	—	—	40.00 "	39.21 "	—	—	"

It is observed that the fall of potential is not regular. Hence it is expected that the solubilized solutions are not rigidly thermodynamically stable^{2,4} and perhaps the soluble charge transfer complexes are formed during solubilization (which is usually evident from spectrum analysis when an absorption band appears in the visible region¹⁶ to be communicated later) due to the following type of intermolecular forces (both attractive and repulsive) caused by the chemical and physical interaction between two or more molecules.

Such attractive forces may be homopolar bonds or hydrogen bonds and even ionic bonds and there may be metallic bonds or secondary bonds due to dispersion, Debye, and Keeson forces while the repulsive forces may be due to Born repulsion, overlapping filled electron shells¹⁵. On studying other properties *e.g.*, dielectric constant, polarisation, etc., a clear picture of the charge transfer complexes will be obtained.

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